

ELECTRICAL GRID SYSTEMS AND CONTROL SYSTEM IN THE WORLD

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Abstract

Electrical grid or power grid is defined as the network which interconnects the generation, transmission and distribution unit. It supplies the electrical power from generating unit to the distribution unit. A large amount of power is transmitted from the generating station to load center at 220kV or higher. The network form by these high voltage lines is called the super grid. The super grid feeds the sub-transmission network operating at 140kV or less.

Key words: Electrical grid, power grid, generation, distribution unit, Electrical substation

An **electrical grid** is an interconnected network for electricity delivery from producers to consumers. Electrical grids vary in size and can cover whole countries or continents. It consists of:

- power stations: often located near energy and away from heavily populated areas
- electrical substations to step voltage up or down
- electric power transmission to carry power long distances
- electric power distribution to individual customers, where voltage is stepped down again to the required service voltage(s). [1]

Grids are nearly always synchronous, meaning all distribution areas operate with three phase alternating current (AC) frequencies synchronized (so that voltage swings occur at almost the same time). This allows transmission of AC power throughout the area, connecting a large number of electricity generators and consumers and potentially enabling more efficient electricity markets and redundant generation.

The combined transmission and distribution network is part of electricity delivery, known as the "**power grid**" in North America, or just "the grid". In the United Kingdom, India, Tanzania, Myanmar, Malaysia and New Zealand, the network is known as the National Grid. [2]

Figure 1: Diagram of an electric power system Generation.

Figure 2: [Turbo generator](#)

Electricity generation is the process of generating [electric power](#) from sources of [primary energy](#) typically at [power stations](#). Usually this is done with [electromechanical generators](#) driven by [heat engines](#) or the [kinetic energy](#) of water or wind. Other energy sources include solar [photovoltaics](#) and [geothermal power](#).

The sum of the power outputs of generators on the grid is the production of the grid, typically measured in [gigawatts](#) (GW). [3]

Transmission

Electric power transmission is the bulk movement of [electrical energy](#) from a generating site, via a web of interconnected lines, to an [electrical substation](#), from which is connected to the distribution system. This networked system of connections is distinct from the local wiring between high-voltage substations and customers.

Because the power is often generated far from where it is consumed, the transmission system can cover great distances. For a given amount of power,

transmission efficiency is greater at higher voltages and lower amperages. Therefore voltages are stepped up at the generating station, at stepped down at local substations for distribution to customers.

Most transmission is [three-phase](#). Three phase, compared to single phase, can deliver much more power for a given amount of wire, since the neutral and ground wires are shared. Further, three-phase generators and motors are more efficient than their single-phase counterparts. [4]

However for conventional conductors one of the main losses are resistive losses which are a square law on current, and depend on distance. High voltage AC transmission lines can lose 1-4% per hundred miles. However, [high-voltage direct current](#) can have half the losses of AC. Over very long distances, these efficiencies can offset the additional cost of the required AC/DC converter stations at each end.

Figure 3: Network diagram of a high voltage transmission system.

Network diagram of a high voltage transmission system, showing the interconnection between the different voltage levels. This diagram depicts the electrical structure of the network, rather than its physical geography.

Transmission networks are complex with redundant pathways. The physical layout is often forced by what land is available and its geology. Most transmission grids offer the reliability that more complex mesh networks provide. Redundancy allows line failures to occur and power is simply rerouted while repairs are done.[5]

[Electrical substation](#)

Substations may perform many different functions but usually transform voltage from low to high (step up) and from high to low (step down). Between the

generator and the final consumer, the voltage may be transformed several times.[6]

The three main types of substations, by function, are:

Step-up substation: these use [transformers](#) to raise the voltage coming from the generators and power plants so that power can be transmitted long distances more efficiently, with smaller currents.

Step-down substation: these transformers lower the voltage coming from the transmission lines which can be used in industry or sent to a distribution substation.

Distribution substation: these transform the voltage lower again for the distribution to end users.

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